

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

РОЛЬ КОНСАЛТИНГОВИХ СЛУЖБ У ПЕДАГОГІЧНІЙ ПІДТРИМЦІ МАЙБУТНІХ УЧИТЕЛІВ В УНІВЕРСИТЕТАХ ТА КОЛЕДЖАХ ВЕЛИКОЇ БРИТАНІЇ

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THE ROLE OF COUNSELING SERVICES IN FUTURE TEACHERS' PEDAGOGICAL SUPPORT IN UNIVERSITIES AND COLLEGES OF GREAT BRITAIN

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АНОТАЦІЯ

У статті проаналізовано основні проблеми консалтингових служб у педагогічній підтримці майбутніх учителів в університетах та коледжах Великої Британії. Представлено університети та коледжі Великої Британії, які надають педагогічну підтримку майбутнім учителям під час їхнього професійного становлення. Охарактеризовано основні ідеї, які покладені в основу консалтингових служб у педагогічній підтримці майбутніх учителів в університетах та коледжах Великої Британії.

ABSTRACT

Main problems of counseling services in future teachers' pedagogical support in universities and colleges of Great Britain are analyzed. Universities and colleges of Great Britain, which provide future teacher with pedagogical support during their professional development are presented. Ideas, which lie in the basis of counseling services in future teachers' pedagogical support in universities and colleges of Great Britain are characterized.

Ключові слова: консалтингові служби, педагогічна підтримка, майбутній учитель, Велика Британія.

Keywords: counseling services, pedagogical support, a future teacher, Great Britain.

Counseling plays an important role in future teacher's professional development in Great Britain.

The British Counseling Association points that a counselor plays a great role in the improving of future teacher's mental health and well-being. A counselor helps people to talk about their feelings, problems, think about their choice and behavior and make some changes in their lives. During meetings with future teachers, counselors try to solve different emotional, psychological and pedagogical problems.

Counseling is not giving an advice, it is a friendly conversation between a counselor and a future teacher. Counselors help future teachers to understand themselves better and to find their own solutions to some problems.

Counseling in Great Britain takes place in different locations such as universities, colleges, schools and also in a private practice [3].

Our research covers the importance of counseling services in British universities and colleges during future teacher's professional development.

In universities and colleges of Great Britain, counseling is considered as an integral part for almost students. There are different counseling services in universities and colleges which support future teachers during their training.

Every university and college has its own website, which contains all the necessary information related to a counseling support. By visiting the websites of universities or colleges, future teachers can find out where they can turn in case of a problem during their studies

or a personal life. In the counseling center of a university or a college, future teachers will get necessary support which they need to overcome some difficulties.

So, let's describe a content of a counseling support of the University of Cambridge. At the university, a counselor provides one-to-one support, support in a small group, mental health counseling support, self-help for specific issues and some workshops.

Counselors provide an individual support to a future teacher who has problems in training and in a personal life. All future teachers, who are studying at a higher educational institution can get a support except those who are abroad. But counselors don't provide support to those who have been deducted from the institution and future teachers of other higher educational institutions.

If future teachers want to get a consultation, they must fill out an online form. A counselor offers a meeting to every future teacher, the duration of which lasts for 75 minutes, during 10 days. If a future teacher is interested in such a meeting, should make an appointment with a counselor as soon as it possible. After four meetings, a counselor decides whether a future teacher needs further support or not.

One-to-one counselor's support must be confidential. Only in extreme cases, a counselor has the right to share the information, if a future teacher is exposed to a significant risk. A counselor records every meeting with a future teacher and the records are stored in a database accessible only to a counselor [6].

A counselor provides psychological support to a future teacher for several weeks but the workshop conducts only once.

Group counseling meetings with future teachers are held weekly for 90 minutes with 8-12 people. Group support is more effective form of a counseling support than an individual support because a group of future teachers can encourage and help to overcome difficulties each other. If future teachers want to go to the workshop, they must register by filling out a registration form. Workshops are held on the Zoom platform.

On the university's website, in the "Group meetings and workshops" section, the schedule of workshops is presented, which includes a topic and date of the workshop. Future teachers have an opportunity to come to one or another workshop and register [6].

Future teachers' psychological health support includes problems deals with person's psychological state that significantly affects at the ability to participate in learning and everyday life. Such a future teachers' support includes support, which is not connected with crisis situations, but with post-crisis situations, when future teachers get help in overcoming difficulties with which they can't cope.

At the University of Cambridge, there is also such a form of a counseling support as self-help. A counseling website has tips that will help future teachers to overcome difficulties on their own, without a specialist's help. Difficulties relate to learning, anxiety, depression, digestive disorders and relationships with other people [6].

The University of Manchester also provides counseling support to future teachers. The institution of higher education offers counseling services which can help future teachers to manage with their psychological health and to identify areas which have an impact on their health.

At the same time, the following psychological problems which are of a great importance to be solved with a consultant are the next: increasing confidence in making decisions, improving interpersonal communication skills, the ability to identify and to manage emotions, increasing self-esteem, communication skills, as well as reducing symptoms of depression [2].

All above mentioned psychological problems are reduced with the help of counseling services at the University of Manchester. Future teachers have the opportunity to get a support from a highly qualified counselor at the institution where they get their higher education. Having any problems, a future teacher can come to a counselor one-to-one, write him a letter to the e-mail address or simply call to make an appointment.

Comparing a counseling support for future teachers at the University of Cambridge and Manchester, we can make a conclusion, that at the University of Manchester there are support hotlines for future teachers at any time of the day. If future teachers feel that they need a counseling support, they can call even at night and get it free of charge and confidentially [2].

So, we can generalized that Cambridge and Manchester universities take care of a counseling support to their future teachers, and also contribute to their professional development in every possible way, helping to

avoid various problems that they faced during their learning and in personal lives.

Oxford University, as one of the best universities in Great Britain, also provides counseling services to future teachers. Counselors provide individual support to future teachers who have problems in their learning and in personal lives. Counseling support can be obtained by a future teacher who is studying at the university for bachelors and master's degrees, also covers postgraduate studies, as well as students who are studying abroad. Future teachers who don't study at the university or who are expelled for certain reasons can't get psychological support from a qualified specialist [5].

In order to get an individual psychological support, future teachers must fill out an online application, which should be submitted only once a year. Every future teacher is offered a 75-minute meeting during 10 working days. Meetings are held online on the Zoom platform or on the third floor of the university, where the counseling service is located.

The Counseling Service is a confidential support service for future teachers which does not tell the information about sessions with future teachers without their permission. Only in extreme cases it is possible, if a future teacher is exposed to a risk.

Group counseling also takes place at Oxford University. Future teachers meet in groups with other future teachers, consisting of 8 to 12 people for several weeks for half an hour. All group consultations and workshops are conducted by experienced consultants [5].

Group counseling is more effective than individual counseling, because during group meetings future teachers can practice different ways of behavior in a safe and supportive environment. In a group, every future teacher can be encouraged and helped to overcome difficulties.

The University of Oxford also has a Mental Health Advisory Service, which helps future teachers to overcome problems related to their mental health that prevent them from taking an active part in their everyday lives.

The Mental Health Advisory Service offers one-on-one support not only to future teachers, but also to teaching staff working at the university [5].

Not only universities, but also colleges pay their attention to the counseling support of future teachers in Great Britain.

Newcastle College provides counseling services to future teachers aged 16 and over. These are usually problems related to studying at a college. Counselors offer various types of a psychological support: a financial support and a support in studying at a college. 16 years old students need support during the period when they leave home and are going to study, it is not always easy. Therefore, counselors should create such a favorable environment so that future teachers feel at home in the institution of higher education and is able to realize their potential. Newcastle College's counseling services are designed to help future teachers to find and to achieve success in their studies and everyday life [4].

The King's College offers cognitive and behavioral, integrative and psychodynamic individual or

group support according to the age and individual characteristics of every future teacher, taking into account gender, language and race.

Counselors suggest future teachers to register on their website and look through the articles posted there. Perhaps some articles will help future teachers to solve their problems.

If a counselor is unable to help a future teacher, there is a hotline where a future teacher can get help, but only in a crisis situation. A counselor can provide support to a future teacher only during working hours and is not in a crisis situation [1].

Therefore, it should be noted that future teachers' counseling in universities and colleges of Great Britain is an important component of their professional development.

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